

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF EXTRACTION METHODS FOR STANDARDIZING GREEN WORMWOOD HERB

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Relevance: Green wormwood herb (*Artemisia viridis* Willd.) is of considerable interest in pharmaceutical practice due to its pronounced biological properties: anti-inflammatory, antiseptic, and choleric. One of the key stages of standardization is the selection of the optimal extraction method that ensures a high yield of biologically active substances while maintaining their stability. In this regard, the study and comparative evaluation of various extraction methods is a relevant task. This study provides a comparative assessment of the effectiveness of various methods for extracting flavonoids from green wormwood herb collected in the highlands of Kyrgyzstan. The study included ultrasonic extraction and Soxhlet extraction. Quantitative determination of the total flavonoid content in green wormwood herb was performed on a Shimadzu spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 410 nm. Using quercetin as a standard, in accordance with the methodology recommended by GF RF XV.

Research objective. To determine the most effective method of extracting green wormwood herb to obtain extracts with the maximum content of biologically active substances suitable for standardization and further pharmaceutical use.

Materials and methods: The object of the study was green wormwood herb collected in the Naryn region of the Kyrgyz Republic at an altitude of 2700-3000 m above sea level in August 2024.

Ultrasonic extraction: extraction was carried out in an ultrasonic bath at a temperature of 40°C for 30 minutes. Water-alcohol solutions of ethanol with concentrations of 40%, 70%, and 96% were used as extractants. Soxhlet apparatus: extraction was carried out for 6 hours using a mixture of ethanol:chloroform:HCl (1:1:0.1). Quantitative determination of the total flavonoid content was carried out spectrophotometrically using the aluminum chloride method. The analysis was performed on a Shimadzu UV-1800 spectrophotometer (Japan) at a wavelength of 410 nm. The calibration curve was constructed using quercetin as a standard sample.

Results. Comparative analysis showed that replacing a simple ethanol extractant with a mixture of ethanol: chloroform:HCl in the Soxhlet method significantly increases the extraction of flavonoids. Chloroform promotes the dissolution of lipophilic components, and acid promotes the hydrolysis of glycosides, releasing aglycones, thereby increasing the total flavonoid content in the extract. This effect explains the higher values obtained by spectrophotometric determination compared to ultrasonic extraction.

Conclusion. Based on the study, it was found that the best results for the flavonoid content in green wormwood herb are achieved by Soxhlet extraction using a mixture of ethanol:chloroform:HCl (1:1:0.1). This method allows for the most efficient extraction of both polar and nonpolar flavonoid compounds and can be recommended for standardizing the technology for extracting biologically active substances from green wormwood herb.